

Spectrophotometric Determination of Phosphorus with *N,N'*-Diphenylbenzamidine and Methylene Blue

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Many spectrophotometric methods for determination of phosphorus based on the formation of heteropoly acid with molybdate have been described. The molar absorptivities of these heteropoly acids in aqueous solution or in organic solvents after solvent extraction, are generally low¹. Several cationic dyes, such as methylene blue, ethyl violet, crystal violet, auramine, malachite green, etc. have also been used for the determination of phosphorus². The spectrophotometric determination of phosphates using the above dyes possesses several disadvantages.

In the present investigation, a sensitive and selective method for determination of phosphorus at trace level is described. The method is based on the development of floated complex of molybdophosphoric acid (MPA) and methylene blue (MB) with *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine³ (DPBA) in toluene and its subsequent dissolution in acetone.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of MPA-MB-DPBA complex formed in toluene-acetone mixture against reagent blank, exhibits an absorbance maximum around 655 nm. Since the absorbance of the reagent blank at this wavelength is negligible, the toluene-acetone (1 : 3) mixed solvent is used as reference for all the measurements. A 0.5–3.0 *M* H₂SO₄ is sufficient for the formation of yellow MPA and maximum floatation with MB and DPBA. In practice, a total of 1 *M* H₂SO₄ was employed throughout the experiment.

The effect of various organic polar and non-polar solvents on the extraction of the floated MPA-MB-DPBA complex were studied. Of these maximum absorbance is observed with benzene but toluene was chosen due to its least toxic nature, higher selectivity and comparable sensitivity of the complex.

Phosphorus reacts with ammonium molybdate to form MPA over an optimum concentration range of $(0.86-6.92) \times 10^{-3}$ *M*. At least 0.0036 *M* DPBA is required for full extraction of MPA-MB complex. An excess DPBA concentration upto 0.014 *M* showed no change in absorbance. Maximum and constant absorbance are obtained when at least 1.3×10^{-4} *M* MB is used. An increased concentration of MB upto 5.3×10^{-4} *M* showed no change in absorbance. A shaking time of 1 min is sufficient for the complete extraction of MPA-MB-DPBA complex. The absorbance of the organic phase remains constant for atleast 4 h. Of the various diluents used only acetone gives complete dissolution of the complex. The order of addition of reagents does not effect the spectral property of the complex.

The MPA-MB-DPBA complex follows Beer's law upto 0.2 μg of phosphorus ml^{-1} . The molar absorptivity of the MPA-MB-DPBA complex, calculated in terms of P, is 1.86×10^5 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at λ_{max} 655 nm. The precision of the method was checked by taking ten replicate

measurements containing 1.0 µg P per 10 ml aqueous phase. The relative standard deviation is found to be 1.4%. The detection limit of P in this method is 3 µg dm⁻³. Sandell's sensitivity of the method is 1.6 × 10⁻⁴ µg cm⁻².

In the present investigation none of the elements like Si, Ge, As, Sb and W which interfered in the earlier methods based on heteropoly acid formation, interfere except As, and the interference of which was masked with 2 ml 1.0% sodium thiosulphate. This is due to the selective extraction of MPA with DPBA in toluene. By use of DPBA as an extracting reagent at least 2000-fold excess of the above mentioned elements can be tolerated in the real samples. The effect of various diverse ions on the extraction of 1.0 µg P was examined. The tolerance limits of the various diverse ions are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF 1.0 µg PHOSPHORUS

Ions added	Tolerance limit* mg
Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	7.5
Mn ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , Hg ^{II}	7.0
Cd ^{II}	6.5
Pb ^{II}	6.0
Sb ^{III}	5.0
W ^{VI} , Fe ^{III}	4.5
U ^{VI} , Sn ^{IV}	4.0
Bi ^{III} , Ce ^{IV} , Th ^{IV}	3.5
Si ^{IV} , Ge ^{IV}	2.0
As ^{V**} , V ^V	1.0
Tartarate, citrate	5.5
Borate, oxalate, acetate	5.0
Thiosulphate	4.5

*Causing an error less than 2%. **Masked with 2 ml 1% Na₂S₂O₃.

The stoichiometry of phosphorus to DBPA and MB was determined by plotting log distribution ratio of P (A/(A_{max}-A)) and log molar concentration of DBPA or MB. The results indicate the formation of a 1 : 1 : 2, P : DPBA : MB complex. The most probable reaction mechanism can be expressed as

Subscripts o and o' denote toluene and toluene-acetone mixture respectively.

Application : The present method was applied for the recovery of P from various standard samples and groundwater samples collected from the different areas in this region.

An accurately weighed standard samples were digested with acids separately as according to the literature⁴. Their volume was adjusted to required concentrations and P content was determined (Table 2).

TABLE 2—RECOVERY OF PHOSPHORUS FROM STANDARD SAMPLES

Standard samples*	Certified P content %	P found by present method %	Relative standard deviation of present method* ±(%)
BAS-5f Brass	0.06	0.062	1.5
6f Gunmetal	0.07	0.073	1.3
BCS/SS, CRM 452/1	0.035	0.038	1.4
Sy-3, Syenite ^a Canada	0.54	0.55	1.5
USGS-BHVO-1 ^a	0.14	0.146	1.5
G-2 ^a	0.25	0.27	1.3

**n = 5. *BAS = Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Newham Hall, Newby, U.K.; USGS = United States Geological Samples, Arlington VA, U.S.A.; BCS-CRM = British Chemical Standard Certified Reference Materials, Newham Hall, Newby, U.K.

^aP reported as P₂O₅.

A known volume of the water samples collected from various regions were treated and pre-concentrated to about half of the original volume. P content was determined according to the procedure described above. The data obtained were compared by AAS and the results were found to be in good agreement with present method (Table 3).

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF PHOSPHORUS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES

Sample	Phosphorus found (mg ml ⁻¹)		Relative standard deviation $\pm\%$
	Present method	AAS	
Tap Water :			
R. S. Univ.	1.1	1.08	1.4
Bhilai	1.32	1.38	1.3
Engg. College, Raipur	1.2	1.16	1.3
Ground Water ^a :			
(A)	0.75	0.73	1.2
(B)	0.62	0.60	1.4
(C)	0.81	0.78	1.4
(D)	0.72	0.71	1.3

* $n = 5$. ^a(A), (B), (C) and (D) are the four points of sampling in the region of Amanaka, Raipur.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss-Jena SPEKOL spectrophotometer with EK-5 attachment used for measuring the absorbance.

A standard solution of phosphorus was prepared by dissolving potassium dihydrogen phosphate (0.1098 g) in distilled water (250 ml). The working standard solutions were prepared by appropriate dilutions. $8.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ or 1.06% (w/v) ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate and $2.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ or 0.1% (w/v) methylene blue solution in distilled water were prepared.⁵ *N,N'*-Diphenylbenzamidine was synthesised⁵ and its $7.35 \times 10^{-3} M$ or 0.2% (w/v) solution in toluene was used for extraction. 5 M sulphuric acid was used for acidity adjustment.

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade (B.D.H., E. Merck).

Procedure : An aliquot of the solution containing upto 2.0 μg P was taken in a 25-ml Nessler's tube and its acidity was adjusted to 1 M with H₂SO₄. Then ammonium molybdate solution (2 ml) was added and the aqueous phase made upto 10 ml. It was allowed to stand for 4 min in a boiling water-bath. The molybdophosphoric acid (MPA) formed was cooled to room temperature, 0.1% MB (1 ml) added and the mixture was equilibrated by shaking with 0.2% DPBA solution (3 ml) in toluene. The aqueous phase was discarded and the floated MPA-MP-DPBA complex obtained at the interphase was washed twice with 1 M H₂SO₄. The floatation in toluene was transferred and diluted to 10 ml with acetone. The absorbance was measured at λ_{max} 655 nm against reagent blank.

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